

The Positive Impacts of Music Therapy on Alzheimer's Disease Patients By Glen Finnie

Abstract

Patients with Alzheimer's Disease suffer from numerous symptoms such as loss of coordination, memory, and communication ability. All of this is due to the effect that beta-amyloid and tau proteins have on the brain. Unfortunately, traditional treatment is expensive and doesn't consistently manage the disease. To help with affordable care for patients, music is an option that costs little to nothing and fights Alzheimer's Disease in many ways. The proteins that affect neurons around the brain are partially cleared, helping to slow the progression of the disease and stop symptoms, as well as decreasing levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, and helping with common sleep problems.

Introduction

Alzheimer's Disease affects millions of American patients, caretakers, friends, and family every year. Patients lose memory, coordination, and the ability to perform everyday tasks independently, which puts stress on caretakers, who are frequently unpaid friends or family ("Caregivers"). More people become affected by Alzheimer's Disease each year, yet, most medicines aren't easily accessible, or affordable, and only help fractionally. However, there is another treatment option that is all of these things: music. Music therapy has numerous benefits for patients and is affordable, accessible, and easy to use at the same time.

Overview of Alzheimer's Disease

The National Institute of Aging (NIA) defines Alzheimer's Disease as, "a brain disorder that slowly destroys memory and thinking skills and, eventually, the ability to carry out the simplest tasks." It can be characterized by progressively worsening symptoms such as challenges with memory, language, problem-solving, and cognitive skills. Alzheimer's patients don't lose their memories or minds though, they simply lose access to them. This brain disorder affects over 6 million Americans and is projected to affect 13.8 million by 2050. Alzheimer's is the most common cause of dementia and was the sixth leading cause of death in America in 2019 (Alzheimer's Association). Despite this, there are currently no known cures for Alzheimer's Disease, and most treatments today don't prevent the progression of the disease. Also, new treatment methods typically take 7 to 12 years to be approved due to the risk of harmful side effects and lengthy regulatory approval processes. Treatments that work effectively against the disease are unaffordable for many patients.

How Does This Disorder Affect the Brain?

Alzheimer's Disease affects the brain through many means and in many different regions. Its main impact is the destruction of neurons and their connections, especially in parts of the brain involved in memory, such as the Hippocampus and Entorhinal Cortex. There are a few ways these neurons are affected. The first is plaque build-up of proteins in the fluid between neurons. This buildup disrupts normal cell functions and is caused by beta-amyloid ("What Happens to the Brain in Alzheimer's Disease?"). Amyloid typically is stored in the cell walls of

our neurons and is used to help repair the neurons when necessary. The problem begins when the proteins are supposed to be recycled by the body. Typically, alpha-secretase breaks the amyloid protein into two pieces, to be properly recycled. However in some instances, for reasons unknown, beta-secretases and gamma-secretases break the same protein twice. This results in three pieces of protein. The body can properly recycle two pieces, but the third part, beta-amyloid, cannot be recycled (Hornberger).

Our neurons then push the excess proteins out of the cell, for the glymphatic system to dispose of. As we age, however, our glymphatic system becomes less efficient in clearing out beta-amyloid, which results in an increased build-up of proteins. When the beta-amyloid molecules are not disposed of, excess proteins begin to stick together forming strings of protein, and eventually plaques (clumps of 1000s of proteins randomly attached). These plaques are extremely difficult for a declining glymphatic system to dispose of, and lead to blockages between neurons in the brain (“What Happens to the Brain in Alzheimer's Disease?”). This is where the Amyloid Cascade Hypothesis comes in. The hypothesis states that beta-amyloid accumulation is what leads to Alzheimer’s Disease, rather than Alzheimer’s leading to the accumulation. That would mean that eliminating these blockages can help alleviate symptoms for patients (Hornberger).

Alzheimer’s Disease also chemically alters tau proteins so that they disrupt normal neuron processes. Tau proteins are typically used to stabilize microtubules in neurons. Without these proteins, neurons would be unable to transport molecules and lose the structural stability microtubules usually provide. This is detrimental for the cells as they will lose stability, and will be deprived of the nutrients they need. In Alzheimer’s patients, when these proteins are chemically altered and stop working, not only do they stop performing their function, but the tau proteins form oligomers, or chains, with each other and become tangled within the neuron (Hornberger). Scientists at the University of Warwick found that introducing tau protein oligomers into healthy neurons led to altered waveforms within just 30 minutes. This leads to slower and shorter signals being transmitted from neuron to neuron. So, faulty tau proteins deprive neurons of the necessary nutrients and form tangles that interfere with normal cell function. Additionally, the Microglia cells that are part of the glymphatic system, and responsible for clearing waste in the brain, fail to dispose of certain waste such as plaques or tau oligomers, due to inflammation of the cells throughout the Alzheimer’s process (Hill).

Alzheimer’s Disease also disrupts the body’s natural circadian system and sleep cycle. In our bodies, the hypothalamus tracks the amount of sunlight being detected by our retinas. When it is exposed to sunlight, the suprachiasmatic nucleus in the hypothalamus is stimulated. This releases serotonin and some other hormones, allowing the body to naturally synchronize cellular activities with daytime. We also have a natural homeostatic sleep drive. This sleep drive builds our desire for sleep the longer we are awake, which helps our bodies fall asleep initially. Once we are asleep, the sleep drive is diminished, and the circadian system decreases alertness throughout the night, which helps us stay asleep for longer. The Circadian System regulates body temperature, melatonin levels, appetite, and cortisol (Guo). However, in Alzheimer’s patients,

the hypothalamus often has difficulty recognizing when it is day and when it is night. This hurts the body's natural schedule for sleep, cellular activity, and metabolism, among other things.

Traditional Medicinal Treatment

Medicine can still be beneficial for Alzheimer's Disease patients. The difference between the effects of these medicines and Music therapy is how they treat Alzheimer's. The medicinal treatments focus on the levels of certain neurotransmitters in the brain, as opposed to Music Therapy, which helps prevent blockages and altered proteins from disrupting brain function. The two main types of treatment for patients are cholinesterase inhibitors and memantine.

Cholinesterase inhibitors help manage levels of acetylcholine, which is naturally depleted in Alzheimer's patients. Acetylcholine is a neurotransmitter that passes signals from neuron to neuron, while also contributing to memory, thought, judgment, and alertness. It moves into the synaptic cleft, the space between neurons, and binds to a nicotinic receptor or muscarinic receptor. This process repeats, transferring the chemical message through the brain. Low levels of acetylcholine are associated with muscle and memory problems. Cholinesterase inhibitors' job is to stop cholinesterase, an enzyme that breaks down acetylcholine at increased rates during Alzheimer's Disease. By preventing cholinesterase from functioning properly, cholinesterase inhibitors can regulate levels of acetylcholine in Alzheimer's patients. Though there are many benefits to taking this medicine, there can be side effects of nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea, and it loses its effectiveness as the disease progresses (Cleveland Clinic).

The second approved medicine for Alzheimer's Disease is Memantine, which is currently the only FDA-approved NMDA receptor antagonist. Memantine is approved for moderate to severe stages of Alzheimer's Disease, and it works to stop excess calcium from entering neurons. Typically, glutamate interacts with an NMDA receptor, which allows a certain amount of calcium to enter the brain cell. This is an essential step in the signaling of neurons and in learning and memory. However, increased levels of glutamate are common in Alzheimer's patients and this allows too much calcium into each neuron. This can lead to overexcited neurons, which eventually results in the death of the cells. Higher levels of glutamate have also been associated with higher pain levels, and it has been associated with stress, anxiety, and seizures. Memantine prevents these from happening by blocking any excess glutamate from accessing the cells, therefore helping to ensure proper cell function (Cleveland Clinic).

Music as an Alternative Therapy

With all of these drug-related financial burdens, time commitments, and negative effects on patients and caregivers, there is still little effective and affordable treatment available. However, music therapy has shown numerous benefits for people with Alzheimer's Disease, which are reflected in the patients' caregivers. First, music therapy has been found to calm agitated patients of Alzheimer's Disease, improve mood, enhance long-term memory, and reduce chronic pain, depression, agitation, wandering, and feelings of isolation. One study helped 5 patients participate in one weekly music therapy session. Each patient was given a personalized selection of instrumental music and measured periodically on their Depression Score (Cornell

Scale) and Anxiety Score (Hamilton Scale), and the Caretaker was measured on the burden they felt (Zarit Scale). After four weeks, the patients' average depression score dropped from 10.8 to 2.2, the average anxiety score went from 9.4 to 3.4, and the burden felt by the caregiver dropped from 30.2 to 15.6 ("Impact of Music Therapy on Anxiety and Depression for Patients with Alzheimer's Disease and on the Burden Felt by the Main Caregiver [Feasibility Study]").

There are also many functions and ways to practice music therapy. The effects differ based on whether we are listening, playing, or composing the music. Music can also be used to help memory, or simply to calm patients and relieve stress. When aiming to improve memory, the effect is greater when the music is self-selected by the patient, which allows them to have deeper and more meaningful emotions and memories. Music therapy has this impact because of all the parts of the brain that relate to music.

Decades of research have revealed that processing music impacts six main areas. These include the Auditory Pathway, Musical-syntactic network, Attention and Working memory network, Motor network, Reward/Emotion Network, and Episodic Memory network. These areas of the brain help us recognize and perceive music, which triggers pleasure and rewarding emotions. Though some of these regions aren't majorly affected by Alzheimer's Disease, they can be activated through music, which helps keep them alive and healthy, and prevents any potential damage. The Episodic Memory network, however, is the most affected. This area of the brain is impaired by Alzheimer's Disease and Dementia, as its main purpose is to recognize music and recall any memories that may be associated with the music. Though it is impaired by Alzheimer's Disease and Dementia, music can help reactivate the Episodic Memory Network, which can help Alzheimer's patients recall memories associated with the music they listen to (Sima).

The second benefit of music therapy is that it helps increase levels of melatonin and norepinephrine significantly in Alzheimer's patients. A study at Miami Veterans Administration Medical Center, in Miami, Florida, followed 20 Alzheimer's patients who had blood samples taken before the experiment. For the next 4 weeks, the patients had 30 to 40-minute music-listening sessions in the morning for 5 days a week. Immediately after the study, the patients were tested again and showed significantly increased levels of melatonin, norepinephrine, and epinephrine. Then, 6 weeks later, even without listening to music between tests, the patients' melatonin levels continued to rise. Norepinephrine and epinephrine levels returned to pre-study levels, however ("Music Therapy Increases Serum Melatonin Levels in Patients with Alzheimer's Disease"). Now, why does this matter? Norepinephrine is a neurotransmitter that is important for processes like digestion and the regulation of the heartbeat. There can be reductions of norepinephrine of up to 50% during the late stages of Alzheimer's Disease, but it is thought that depleted norepinephrine can contribute to the behavioral complications seen in Alzheimer's patients, and norepinephrine imbalance has been linked to the obstruction of memory (Rogers).

Melatonin is a hormone that helps our bodies fall asleep, and is controlled by the hypothalamus. When nighttime is detected, the suprachiasmatic nucleus sends a signal to the

pineal gland to begin the release of melatonin. The problem is that Alzheimer's patients' bodies have difficulty detecting when nighttime is, as the hypothalamus doesn't function properly in brains affected by Alzheimer's Disease. This leads to improper sleep schedules for Alzheimer's patients. Researchers in Malaysia have found that melatonin helps with sleep disturbances for Alzheimer's patients, among other benefits. While melatonin can be delivered to patients in supplements, some participants in a study showed signs of social isolation and complained of depression when given supplements. Research has also shown that melatonin helps Alzheimer's patients stabilize their circadian rhythm, which helps with the sleep cycle and other bodily processes. This has a deeper effect though. Studies show that sleep deprivation is linked to further build-up of beta-amyloid. This is because the glymphatic system, the brain's dedicated waste system, works mostly during sleep ("Sleep Deprivation Increases Alzheimer's Protein."). When the glymphatic system doesn't have time to clear out beta-amyloid, more plaques accumulate, which leads to worsening symptoms of Alzheimer's, including bad sleep, which leaves the glymphatic system less time yet again. This vicious cycle continues until something can try to stop it ("How Sleep Clears the Brain").

Music vs. Medicine

Music therapy and Medicine can be used together to benefit Alzheimer's patients in different ways. While medicine helps manage levels of neurotransmitters in the brain, music therapy focuses mostly on the circadian system and sleep cycle. The medicine helps manage levels of neurotransmitters in Alzheimer's patients, which helps to block or delay some symptoms, but it doesn't prevent the advancement of Alzheimer's Disease. While music therapy is extremely affordable, accessible, and easy to use, it also only improves certain aspects of an Alzheimer's-infected brain. Since medicine and music benefit separate parts of the brain, and work in different ways, music therapy should not be used as a replacement for medicine. With that being said, whether or not a patient is receiving treatment in the form of medicine, music therapy will help manage other aspects of the disease and will help the patient decrease levels of anxiety, stress, and depression.

Conclusion

Alzheimer's Disease is a brain disorder that affects millions of people in the US alone. This disease takes over the lives of the patients and the lives of care-giving friends and family. It is a leading cause of death and dementia and causes stress for all parties involved. Not only this, but treatments today are either ineffective, unaffordable, or have harmful side effects. Music therapy offers a counter-balancing solution to all of this. It is proven to improve patients' moods and decrease levels of depression, stress, and anxiety for both caregivers and people with Alzheimer's Disease. All while being very accessible, easy to use, affordable, and with no side effects. As professor of neurology, Oliver Sacks said, "Music can lift us out of depression or move us to tears – it is a remedy, a tonic, orange juice for the ear. But for many of my neurological patients, music is even more – it can provide access, even when no medication can, to movement, to speech, to life. For them, music is not a luxury, but a necessity."

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